

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14578736

Relationship between Welfare Implementation and Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Gbawa, Beatrice¹ & Daisey. I. Dimkpa²

^{1,2}Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling,
Faculty of Education,

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

¹Email:gbawabeatrice@gmail.com/ Phone No: 08063560792

ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between welfare implementation and job satisfaction of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. A correlational research design was selected for this investigation. The study's population included 708 teachers from public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size was calculated using the Taro Yamane formula, resulting in a sample of 250 teachers. The stratified random sampling procedure was used, and the instruments for this study were two researcher-designed questionnaire titled 'Teachers' Welfare Implementation Questionnaire (TWIQ) and 'Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire '(TJSQ)'. The instrument's reliability, measured using Cronbach's alpha, was 0.93 and 0.83, respectively. Mean and standard deviation were used to address the research questions, while the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was employed to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. The study's results indicated that fringe benefits, welfare packages, and in-service training significantly improved teachers' job satisfaction. Additionally, there was a strong positive correlation between fringe benefits, welfare packages, and in-service training with teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study recommended that government should through the Ministry of Education provide monetary and non-monetary incentives alongside with cars for teachers, implement an upward review of policy on teachers' welfare packages and funds for in-service training of teachers at the secondary school level.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, public secondary schools, teachers, welfare implementation

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are crucial stakeholders in the Secondary education system in Nigeria, and their role in creating and imparting knowledge cannot be overemphasized. Teachers are responsible for translating educational policies into practical school activities, interact with students on daily basis, and play a crucial role in guaranteeing that the intended educational outcomes are achieved. Because of the central role that teachers play in the educational system, the FRN (2014) policy was developed, which states that no education can surpass the calibre of its teachers and suggests some measures to improve the efficient and effective instruction profession. These steps include maintaining a functional and motivated teacher workforce in the educational system through recruitment of qualified teachers and enhancing their welfare. Surprisingly, there seems to be a wide difference between policy formulation and policy implementation with regards to how teachers are maintained and motivated in the educational system. It is disconcerting to consider that a nation with 63 colleges of education four privately owned, 38 state-owned, and 21 federally owned as well as over 200 universities may be suffering from a shortage of skilled, dedicated, and productive educators (Ogu, 2016).

This situation seems to be more pronounced in Rivers State Planning Commission as cited in Echikpu (2022) who submits that Rivers State public servants had their last promotion in 2010, and that up till now, there has been no implementation of the promotion, no promotion increment via payment, no employment and many teachers have retired without replacement. Given this scenario, it seems there are current public outcry regarding dearth of qualified teachers as many secondary schools in the state lack instructors in major academic areas including Mathematics, English Language, Physics, Chemistry, and so forth. The researcher observes it in Rivers State that some secondary schools have inadequate teachers to teach all the subjects offered in the schools, while others do.

The problem of teachers' job satisfaction though a worldwide educational issue seems to constitute a big problem in Rivers State. When teachers move out of the school system, it constitutes wastage to the educational system. Due to attrition, schools and the education system as a whole suffer as the secondary education system is losing staff members whose abilities, qualifications, and performance are important assets to the operation, expansion, and development of schools.

Retention is a concept that denotes how an organization or institution manages its workforce, and relates to a state or a circumstance of enticing and enabling individuals to work satisfactorily, stay with, and contribute significantly to the growth and productivity of their organizations (Agboola & Offiong, 2018).

Teachers' job satisfaction is an action taken to control teachers' turnover (teachers mobility and attrition) by ensuring that teachers do not sign at least one additional contract anywhere beyond their initial contract with the school system. (Kelly, 2014). It may involve all practices aimed at maintaining a functional teacher workforce in school, such that they become unwilling to move out to other professions (attrition) or move voluntarily to other schools (mobility). Agboola and Offiong (2018) submitted that teachers' retention helps to prevent disruptions in education, particularly when they leave their jobs or a school during the academic year or after they have already been involved in important school projects. Retaining qualified employees is important because their departure could negatively impact productivity and service delivery.

The tendency for teachers to leave the school system seems to be heightened where there is low teachers' usage, absence of clear career path, financial insecurity, and poor compensation, etc. In the school system, incentive package has the capacity to arouse teachers' motivation, satisfaction and disposition to perform at the peak of their ability, thus, may reduce the tendencies for teachers to leave the school system for other professions or jobs. Dixit and Bhati (2012) maintain that bad rewards package has been a crucial issue determining employees' commitment, productivity and retention in an organization. Poor compensation, inadequate opportunity for development, irregular promotion, incompatible welfare package, poor working condition, financial insecurity and absence of clear career path may trigger teachers' dissatisfaction and negative behaviour among workers. In Rivers State, there have been issues of irregular payment of teachers' salaries, poor salary structure, irregular promotion, nonpayment of promotion arrears, poor training programmes for teachers, personal and professional development and nonpayment of allowances due to teachers on time, may legally explain the observed negative work behaviour of teachers in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Teachers' satisfaction, motivation, commitment, performance and disposition to stay in any school organization are largely influenced by incentive package/management put in place by the school system (Ogu, 2016).

Welfare implementation refers to the monetary and non-monetary system adopted by some institutions to reward subordinates on their efforts. Ogu, (2016) submits that the purpose of incentive packages is to encourage employees to work harder on their assigned tasks by offering them financial or non-monetary rewards. The goal of incentive packages is to maximise employee performance and retain the most productive workers (Arnold, 2013). Educational institutions may be at risk when workers are underpaid, not compensated for incidental contributions, promotions are delayed excessively, the workplace is uninspiring, and teachers are not exposed to new information in their areas of expertise (Besong, 2015). It means that the incentive package applied by the school system has significant implication on how the system is able to enhance teachers' retention in schools and reduce their mobility to other jobs for better offer.

When teachers are recognized for extra efforts, compensated based on performance, promoted as at when due, provided with conducive work environment and functional facilities, and given compatible

welfare packages and so on, they tend to be happy and express readiness to stay in the school system and exhibit positive attitude towards their task in schools. On the other hand, when teachers' promotion is delayed, no adequate welfare package, teachers are not properly recognized for extra effort exerted on their jobs, compensation is not commensurate with performance and so on, teachers tend to leave either the teaching profession in search for better offers or exhibit all manner of negative attitude in school. However, recognition, fringe benefit regular promotion, conducive work environment, compatible welfare scheme, and in-service training are incentive packages that may have implications on teachers' retention in the school system.

Statement of the Problem

Due to the fact that trained teachers are churned out every year, schools still have a low level of teacher satisfaction. This has therefore created a lot of concern among parents, students, school officials and the government. This low level of job satisfaction among teachers especially in the public school has both direct and indirect implication on the student's performance. There is some time to find the good substitutes in the school when the experienced teachers leave the school. The high staff turnover rate has been attributed to the recent decline in the academic performance of schools. In Rivers State there is also a number of questions that can be asked if the factors that influence teacher job satisfaction in the schools are different from those of other states. This study also found that some teachers in the secondary schools have demonstrated their lack of motivation to perform their duties by absenting themselves from school on one pretext or the other to engage in business activities.

This negative perception towards work may therefore have to mean that these teachers are very unhappy with their jobs. The problem of teacher attrition has become one of the most predictable yet intractable challenges in education system in schools. This has created the need for the researcher to find out the relationship between welfare implementation and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between welfare implementation and job satisfaction of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In view of this, the study is specific objectives were to;

1. determine the influence of fringe benefits on teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the influence of welfare packages on teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. examine the influence of in-service training on teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

1. To what extent does fringe benefits enhance teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does welfare packages enhance teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does in-service training enhance teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and statistically tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference between welfare packages and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant difference between n-service training and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Conceptual Review

Welfare Implementation

Welfare is an act of or promise for greater activity. It is sometimes termed a stimulant to increased action. In addition to earnings, welfare is something that is provided. Welfare is still impacted by a number of factors that are creating some significant trends in worker compensation, regardless of how laws affect salaries generally. Aligning wages with the objectives of the organisation is one of these trends (Don, 2013). Organisations care about what has to be done to help employees reach and maintain high performance levels. Employees can be motivated in a variety of ways outside their pay, which is their legal entitlement. These consist of a profit-sharing plan, bonuses, incentives, and rewards. The goal is to create a work environment and motivation process that will guarantee and increase employee productivity in line with the organization's goal. Others include; structuring remuneration to meet the needs of the employees, improved remuneration, and equal pay for equal work (Fisk, 2001).

Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction among teachers refer to the degree of pleasure or contentment experienced by teachers in relation to their job roles, responsibilities, and the environment in which they work. A teacher's job satisfaction is influenced by various factors such as salary, working conditions, professional growth opportunities, support from administration, recognition, and relationships with colleagues and students (Bolin, 2007). High job satisfaction can lead to increased motivation, commitment, and effectiveness in teaching, whereas low satisfaction can result in burnout and turnover. Understanding and addressing the factors that affect teachers' job satisfaction is crucial for educational institutions aiming to provide optimal learning experiences for students.

Fringe Benefits

Erabasi (2012) defines fringe benefits as pay that is provided in addition to direct earnings or salary. Examples of these benefits include paid holidays, pension plans, corporate cars, home allowances, health insurance, and subsidised meals. Bernandin (2007) avers that fringe benefits are those items that have direct financial value to the individual employee such as gratuity, Christmas bonus, among others. Justifying this, Ogu, (2016) defined fringe benefits as those benefits that are additional, not earned, and are usually provided to all employees of an organization regardless of their performance or output such as annual leave, salary advance, educational assistance among others. But the aim of fringe benefits is to enhance the economic welfare of employees and in doing so, enhance staff retention (Bernandin, 2007).

Welfare Packages

Welfare packages are strategies employed by work organizations to motivate employees for better job performance. The third category of the organizational reward system is welfare and social benefits services, some of which are statutory and others are voluntary. Some of the most important quantitative characteristics of employment which is directly related to the quality of workers' work life and their productivity depend on sufficient earnings, safe and humane working conditions, and access to basic social security benefits (Keitany, 2014). Welfare may be defined as a state of affairs that is positive in the sense that it entails positive physical, psychological, moral and emotional condition. As pointed out by Abu (2016) Employee welfare can be defined as any action taken by the employer to enhance the quality of life of the workmen. Nzelibe (2011) argued that welfare packages are extra benefits awarded to employees for being members of an organization, on the other hand Okumbe (2010) and Abbah (2014) stated that organization that offers welfare packages is keen on creating a good working environment in which employees are aware that they are valued. Arsmtrong (2008) stated that the logic of welfare scheme is to develop effective, healthy, loyal and satisfied employees for the organization to improve its performance. The main goal of welfare packages to encourage employees, get access to utilities and financial benefits due to the work done for the advancement of the organization.

In-Service Training

This paper therefore recommends that there is the need to provide adequate training to teachers to enable them to cope with the increasing challenges of teaching in Rivers State, Nigeria and indeed, the global society. No systematic effort has been made to ensure that, the teacher is updated regularly with the introduction of new knowledge and skills aligned with the updated school curriculum has

impacted the quality of teaching in schools (Odeyemi, 2011). To address this challenge, in-service training is essential. According to Eduwen (2016), in-service training refers to the courses and activities undertaken by practicing teachers to improve their professional knowledge, skills, and competence within the teaching profession. According to Okolo in a research conducted in 2013, in-service training is a kind of professional development where the employees are offered some training or education while still in their working station. In-service training aims at the human resource development of the school system and the educational organisation in particular. For teachers to carry out their duties in the most appropriate manner, it becomes necessary for them to demand new skills and techniques, making them more professional in their roles. For educators, in-service training might address new teaching methods, curriculum changes, technology integration, classroom management strategies, such training is essential for keeping professionals update with the most recent advancements in their field and ensuring the delivery of high quality services (Udofia & Ikpe, 2012).

Fringe Benefits and Teachers' Job Satisfaction

It is in this light that the remuneration system of any organization will be the focus of this paper in as far as the success and sustainability of the organization is concerned. The reward systems and motivating incentives will define the degree of commitment of the employees and their attitude at work. First of all, there is fringe benefit. Fringe benefits are those benefits which are provided alongside wages or salaries, these benefits include a company car, housing allowance, medical insurance, paid leave, pension plans, subsidized meals, health insurance, group life insurance, educational support, childcare, and reimbursement for assistance (Don, 2013).

Welfare Packages and Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Welfare packages refer to the benefits, apart from regular salary, provided to employees by their organizations. These benefits can include health insurance, housing allowances, paid vacations, retirement benefits, transportation allowances, bonuses, and more. The primary aim of welfare package is to improve the overall well-being of employees, fostering a sense of loyalty, enhancing job satisfaction, and ensuring that the organization remains competitive in attracting top talents (Ajayi & Ogunyemi, 2016). Teachers, like any other professionals, greatly value welfare packages. In the context of education, welfare packages might also encompass training opportunities, subsidized education for their children, sabbatical leaves, or even reduced workload periods. Given the inherently stressful nature of teaching, with responsibilities like managing large classes, addressing diverse student needs, and meeting administrative requirements, a comprehensive welfare package can play a crucial role in ensuring job satisfaction among teachers (Oluwole, 2015).

The connection between welfare packages and teachers' job satisfaction have been the subject of various studies and research has shown a direct correlation between the two. For instance, in a study by Bernandin (2007), it was shown that among secondary school teachers, there is a substantial correlation between welfare benefits and work satisfaction. When teachers perceive that their welfare is taken care of, they are more satisfied with their jobs, more committed, and more likely to perform optimally.

In-service Training and Teachers' Job Satisfaction

In-service training refers to ongoing professional development opportunities offered to teachers during their employment, rather than before they begin their teaching career. Teachers receive the skills and information they need from this course, and strategies to address current classroom challenges, implement new pedagogical techniques, and stay updated with educational research and technology. By continually holding their professional skills, teachers can effectively respond to the evolving demands of the education sector and the diverse needs of their students. Additionally, in-service training often provides a platform for teachers to interact, collaborate, and share experiences with their peers. This collaborative environment not only facilitates the exchange of best practices but also fosters a supportive community, further contributing to job satisfaction (Bolin, 2007). Good in-service training improves teachers' work happiness, which raises student success and prepares schools to adapt to a variety of changes. In contrast to pre-employment training, in-service training can impact all already employed instructors, potentially having a more immediate and extensive effect on the overall efficacy of the teaching workforce (Udofia & Ikpe, 2012).

Theoretical Review

The Two-factor or motivation-hygiene theory was published by Frederick Herzberg in 1959 to explain factors that can influence workers' motivation, job satisfaction and behaviour in organizations. The theory is referred to as Herzberg's two-factor theory of workplace motivation because it is based on two categories of factors: satisfiers, or motivation factors, and dissatisfiers, or hygiene factors. According to Herzberg's theory, the satisfiers or motivation factors are intrinsic to the work and have the capacity to induce workers to result-oriented behaviour, leading to high level of motivation and job satisfaction, while the dissatisfiers or hygiene factors are extrinsic or environmental to the job carried out by workers and have the capacity to cause demotivation, negative behaviour and employees' job dissatisfaction.

The theory has relevance to this study in the sense that it explains the factors at work places that will naturally boost employees' satisfaction and morale towards effective performance, and thus arouse their disposition to remain in the job. It also explains other factors which can reduce employees' satisfaction and morale towards high performance, thereby causing all manner of poor behaviour at work. It means that to ensure high job satisfaction and positive attitude of teachers towards their assigned tasks in school, effort should be made to remove those factors that can give employees (teachers) dissatisfaction or engender intrapersonal conflicts, and promote those that can enhance teachers' satisfaction and positive attitude towards their assigned tasks in the school system for maximum performance. This implies that factors such as recognition, regular promotion, conducive working environment, good pay, etc may boost teachers' positive attitude in the school system.

Empirical Review

Ngatia (2015) in a study on the author explored the impact of fringe benefits on employee job satisfaction and concluded that a well-designed reward package significantly affects both job satisfaction and performance. When employers focus on non-financial reward tools, such as work-life balance, career advancement opportunities, and educational support, employees may feel that the organization is genuinely supporting them.

Al-Otaibi (2017) found that both material and moral incentives influence the performance of administrative staff at the General Authority for Applied Education and Training in Kuwait. However, Al-Otaibi also discovered that moral incentives have a minimal effect on administrative performance. Similarly, this study found that when employees are dissatisfied with material incentives, their performance remains low and unchanged. However, when material and moral incentives are combined, they have a significant impact on performance of administrators to maintain organizational performance. Consequently, managers should focus on adequate plus fair compensation and material reward systems. Therefore, it is also crucial to focus on offering morale support and moral life to ensure that they work harder in order to increase organizational performance.

In a study conducted by Okafor (2015) titled "Impact of welfare packages on teacher performance in Rivers State secondary schools", the aim was to investigate how the provision of welfare packages influenced the teaching performance of secondary school teachers in Rivers State. Adopting a quantitative approach, the research surveyed 500 secondary school teachers from 50 different schools across Rivers State using structured questionnaires. The findings revealed that 78% of teachers who received comprehensive welfare packages reported increased motivation and teaching effectiveness. Moreover, schools with robust welfare provisions recorded 35% better overall academic performance compared to those with minimal or no welfare provisions. The study found that teachers' welfare packages and their effectiveness as teachers in Rivers State secondary schools are directly positively correlated.

Udom (2017) in "Teachers' welfare and its implications for professional competency in Rivers State schools" sought to determine the extent to which teachers' welfare affects their professional competency and delivery in the classroom. Using qualitative research method, the study involved in-depth interviews with 150 teachers and 50 school administrators. The results indicated that teachers in schools with consistent welfare packages displayed enhanced classroom management skills, better lesson delivery, and improved student-teacher relationships. Furthermore, administrators acknowledged that schools with regular welfare benefits had reduced teacher turnover and increased teacher commitment. The research concluded that consistent welfare packages not only retained

quality teachers, but also enhanced their professional competency, which directly impacted students' learning.

Chidiebere (2019) carried out a study titled "Evaluating the role of welfare packages in teacher job satisfaction and retention in Rivers State", which aimed to evaluate the role welfare packages played in job satisfaction and the retention of teachers. Utilizing a mixed- method approach, the research combined the use of questionnaires distributed to 600 teachers and focus group discussions with selected educators. The findings highlighted that schools with regular and substantial welfare packages had a 40% higher teacher retention rate over three years. There was also a strong correlation between job satisfaction levels and the quality of welfare packages provided. The study concluded that effective welfare packages were crucial for both increasing job satisfaction among teachers and ensuring their long-term retention, subsequently impacting the overall quality of education.

In the study carried out by Ekundayo (2018) titled "Assessing the interplay between teacher welfare and student performance in secondary schools of Rivers State," the researcher tried to determine how welfare packages for teachers directly or indirectly influenced students' outcomes. Using a correlational research design, Ekundayo sampled 700 students and their corresponding teachers across 20 schools. It found that schools where teachers reported a high level of satisfaction with their welfare packages and had students scoring 20% higher on standardized tests. The conclusion drawn was that there existed a significant relationship between teachers' welfare and students' performance, suggesting that investment in teachers' welfare could indirectly boost students' academic outcomes.

Igbogi (2018) conducted a study, titled "Welfare provisions as a determinant of teacher commitment in Rivers State secondary education sector." This research aimed to ascertain whether welfare provisions influenced the level of commitment teachers exhibited towards their duties. Through a qualitative case study approach, Igbogi interviewed 80 teachers from 10 secondary schools. The findings emphasized that teachers with access to better welfare packages exhibited higher commitment in terms of lesson planning, extracurricular involvement, and overall dedication to the teaching profession. Igbogi concluded that welfare provisions significantly influenced the dedication and commitment of teachers to their roles.

In a study titled "Teachers' perception of welfare packages and its impact on pedagogical approaches," conducted by Nwankwo (2016), the researcher aimed to understand how teachers perceived various welfare packages and how this perception altered their teaching methodologies. Gathering data from 300 teachers using a combination of questionnaires and observational methods, it was found that those who perceived their welfare packages as adequate and fair, leaned more towards innovative, student-centered pedagogical methods. Conversely, those unsatisfied with their welfare were more likely to use traditional lecture-based approaches. Nwankwo concluded that the perception of fairness and adequacy in welfare packages played a role in a teachers' choice of teaching methodology. The review of empirical studies in relation to teachers' in-service training and job satisfaction was not captured as one of the requirements for teachers' satisfaction. Thus, this is the gap that the present study has identified and filled.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the correlational research design. This was chosen because it tried to ascertain the extent to which variations in one variable are associated with another (Okendu, 2012, Wali, 2016, Elendu, 2010) 708 instructors from public senior secondary schools in Rivers State made up the study's population (Research and Statistics Department, 2022). There are three senatorial districts in Rivers State. At least one secondary school was chosen from each of the three senatorial districts—Rivers East, South East, and South West—using stratified random sampling. 250 instructors made up the study's sample size, which was determined using the Taro Yamane formula. The multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted, and instruments for the study consisted of two self-developed questionnaire. The first is titled Teachers' Welfare Implementation Questionnaire (TWIQ), and the second was titled 'Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ) respectively. The instrument is divided into two sections. Section A was for the demographic profile of the respondents, and Section B of TWIQ consists of three sections related to the research study variables. The first part evaluates aspects of teachers' fringe benefits, the second is for teachers' welfare packages and the third for in-service training, having a total of 15 items. The TJSQ on the other hand consists of 5 items evaluating

teachers' satisfaction with their job. The response pattern was were given a four point rating scale consisting of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) =2 and Very Low Extent (VLE) =1.respectively. The instrument was validated by the supervisor and two experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, Rivers State University. The instruments were pilot tested using thirty teachers who were not part of the sample of the study, and the reliability coefficient was 0.93 for the TWIQ and 0.83 for the TJSQ respectively, using Cronbach Alpha method. The results indicated that the two instruments are reliable. The data was collected by the researcher himself with the help of two trained research assistants using the instruments. In the analysis of the research questions, Mean and Standard deviation was used while for the hypothesis testing, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for research questions were that any item with a mean score of 2.50 and above was considered agreed or accepted, while those below 2.50 was considered disagree or rejected. On the other hand, the decision rule for the test of hypotheses was that if the calculated value of r-statistics is greater than the critical value, we should not accept the null hypothesis.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *To what extent does fringe benefits enhance teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on Fringe Benefits and Teachers' Job Satisfaction
N = 250

S/N	Fringe Benefits	Statement	Response		
			Mean	SD	Decision
1.		Teachers have access to health insurance coverage which keeps them in good health to do their job well	3.00	0.71	VHE
			3.00	0.60	VHE
2.		Pensions are paid when teachers retire from service			
3.		Teachers have access to loan schemes which enables them to acquire cars	2.83	0.38	HE
4.		They enjoy leave bonuses added to their salaries.	2.42	0.50	LE
5.		Teachers are paid retirement benefits as at when due	2.42	1.10	LE
Grand Mean			2.73	0.66	HE

According to the result in Table 1, the respondents accepted that teachers have access to health insurance coverage which keeps them in good health to do their job well (3.00); Pensions are paid when teachers retire from service (3.00); and teachers have access to loan schemes which enables them to acquire cars (2.83) to a very high extent, that is item (1, 2 and 3) to a very high extent. However, they did not accept item (4 and 5), stating that Teachers enjoy leave bonuses added to their salaries (2.42); and teachers are paid retirement benefits as at when due (2.42) respectively. The conclusion, judging from the grand mean score of 2.73 showed that fringe benefits enhanced teachers job satisfaction to a high extent in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: *To what extent does welfare packages enhance teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on Welfare Packages and Teachers Job Satisfaction
N = 250

S/N	Welfare Packages	Statement	Response		
			Mean	SD	Decision
6	Regular payment of salary makes teachers to perform well.		2.56	0.51	HE
7	Prompt promotion increases teachers' working morale.		3.29	0.46	VHE
8	A raise in salary makes teachers to work harder.		2.83	0.38	HE
9	Paid medical expenses of teachers encourages them to be loyal..		2.54	0.51	HE
10	Provision of a good working environment increases teachers' productivity.		2.56	0.51	HE
Grand Mean			2.76	0.47	HE

According to the result in Table 2, the respondents accepted all the items, that regular payment of salary makes teachers to perform their jobs well (2.56), Prompt promotion increases teachers' working morale (3.29), a raise in salary makes teachers to work harder (2.83), paid medical expenses encourage teachers to be loyal (2.54), and provision of good working environment increases teachers' productivity (2.56), that is item (6,7,8,9 and 10), as their mean scores were above 2.50. Also, the grand mean score of (2.76) is indicative of the fact that welfare packages enhanced teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question Three: *To what extent does in-service training enhance teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on In-service Training and Teachers' Job Satisfaction
N = 250

S/N	In-service training	Statement	Response		
			Mean	SD	Decision
11	Participating in induction and orientation training helps to improve the way teachers handle their classes.		3.00	0.71	VHE
12	Giving teachers opportunity to attend seminars/workshops helps them to learn new methods of teaching leading to students' positive academic performance		3.00	0.60	VHE
13	On-the-job training has brought about improvement in the way teachers manage students' behaviour.		2.83	0.38	HE
14	Refresher training provides teachers with intellectual and professional background adequate for their assessment and commitment to the teaching profession.		2.42	0.50	LE
15	Career development training is always organized to improve teachers' productivity.		2.42	1.10	LE
Grand Mean			2.73	0.66	HE

In Table 3, the result shows that only three out of the five items were accepted by the respondents such as participating in induction and orientation training helps to improve the way teachers handle their classes (3.00); giving teachers opportunity to attend workshops and seminars helps them to learn new methods of teaching leading to students' positive academic performance (3.00); and on-the-job training has brought about in the way teachers manage students' behaviour (2.83), that is item (11, 12 and 13). On the other hand, the respondents did not accept that refresher training provides teachers with intellectual and professional background adequate for their assessment and commitment to the teaching profession (2.42) and that career development training is always organized to improve teachers' productivity (2.42), as indicated in item (12 and 15) respectively. The grand mean of (2.73)

is also higher than 2.50, which shows a high level of acceptance. Based on the results, the conclusion drawn is that. In-service training enhanced teachers’ job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent.

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on Teachers’ Job Satisfaction
N = 250

S/N	Job Satisfaction Statement	Response		
		Mean	SD	Decision
16	Verbal compliments such as ‘well-done’, nice performance,’ is pertinent to teachers’ job retention	2.50	0.71	HE
17	When supervisors and colleagues verbally appreciate good performance, it encourages teachers’ commitment to their job	3.00	0.87	VHE
18	At work, colleagues and supervisors who are concerned about fellow teachers help to increase positive interpersonal relationships on occasions such as birthdays, child birth and wedding anniversaries.	3.00	0.60	VHE
19	When supervisors give regular feedback to the teachers under them, it increases their ability to do more work..	2.76	0.65	HE
20	When teachers are paid salaries that reflect their skills and experience, It increases job satisfaction.	3.36	0.77	VHE
Grand Mean		2.92	0.72	HE

In Table 4, the result shows that all the five items were accepted by the respondents such as verbal compliments such as ‘well done’, nice performance, is pertinent to teachers’ job retention, (2.50), when supervisor and colleagues verbally appreciate good performance, it encourages teachers commitment to their job (3.00), At work, colleagues and supervisors who are concerned about fellow teachers help to increase positive interpersonal relationships on occasions such as birthdays, child birth and wedding anniversaries (3.00), when supervisors give regular feedback to the teachers under them, it increases their ability to do more work (2.76), and when teachers are paid salaries that reflect their skills and experience, it increases job satisfaction (3.36), that is items (16, 17, 18, 19 and 20), as their mean scores were above 2.50. Also, the grand mean score of (2.92) is indicative of the fact that welfare implementation enhanced teachers’ job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state to a high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers’ job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation on Relationship between Fringe Benefits and Teachers’ Job Satisfaction in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

		Correlations		
		Fringe Benefits	teachers job satisfaction	Decision
Fringe Benefits teachers job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation		1	Rejected
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.662	
	N	250	250	
	Pearson Correlation	.662	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	250	250	

*S= Significant p<0.05

Table 5 below presents the result of the SPSS analysis that reveals the relationship between fringe benefits and teachers’ job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This was further supported by the Pearson correlation coefficient which was significant at .05 level of significant, r = .662 this shows that there is a strong positive relationship between fringe benefits and

teachers job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In addition, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State was also NOT accepted and the alternate hypothesis accepted [(P =.000) p<0.05]

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between welfare packages and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 6: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation on Relationship between Welfare Packages and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

		Correlations		
		Welfare Packages	Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Decision
Welfare Packages	Pearson Correlation		1	Rejected
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.820	
	N	250	250	
			.000	
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.820	1	Rejected
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.820	
	N	250	250	
			.000	

***S= Significant p<0.05**

Table 6 below is the result from the SPSS analysis of the relationship between welfare packages and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings also reveal that Pearson correlation coefficient show positive correlation between the two variables $r = .820$, it shows that there is a correlation between welfare packages and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Also, the null hypothesis that was formulated assumed that there is no significant correlation between welfare packages and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State was not supported, and the alternative hypothesis was accepted [(P =.000) p<0.05].

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between in-service training and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 7: Pearson's Product Moment on Relationship between in-service Training and Teachers Job Satisfaction in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

		Correlations		
		In-Service Training	Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Decision
In-Service Training	Pearson Correlation		1	Rejected
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.662	
	N	250	250	
			.000	
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.662	1	Rejected
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.662	
	N	250	250	
			.000	

***S= Significant p<0.05**

The result from SPSS analysis in Table 7, the research work also maps out the correlation between in-service training and teachers' job satisfaction in the public senior secondary schools of Rivers State. The use of Pearson correlation coefficient established that there is a significant positive relationship between the two variables; $r = .662$ which implies that there a high positive relationship between in-service training and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Also, the null hypothesis stated that there is no significance relationship between in-service training and teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State was therefore not accepted while the alternate hypothesis was accepted [(P =.000) p<0.05].

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding concerning fringe benefits and job satisfaction of teachers' in research question one indicated that fringe benefits enhance teachers' job satisfaction to a very high extent in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Hypothesis one showed that there was a strong positive relationship between fringe benefits and job satisfaction of teachers. This implies that fringe benefits have effect on teachers' efficiency and effectiveness, as it improves teachers' morale, commitment, job satisfaction and performance. It is pertinent therefore to note that if fringe benefits are provided to teachers in pursuit of their duties, it will ultimately enhance teachers' performance. On the other hand, it may lead to low performance and in most cases attrition, strikes, absenteeism with resultant effects on students' performance outcomes. This result is consistent with the research of Al-Otaibi (2017), which discovered that the efficiency of the administrative staff employed by the General Authority for Applied Training and Education in the state of Kuwait is influenced by both monetary and moral incentives. Additionally, if employees are not satisfied with material incentives, the study indicated that their performance would be low and will not increase. On the other hand, the strong positive relationship found between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in the present study aligns with that of Nwankwo (2016) which suggested that teachers' perception of fairness and adequacy in benefits, including fringe benefits, played a role in their overall job satisfaction and teaching methodology.

Findings of the second research question on welfare packages and welfare packages significantly increase teachers' work happiness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, according to data on teacher job satisfaction in these institutions. Additionally, hypothesis two demonstrated a high positive correlation between work satisfaction and welfare packages. This implies that welfare package in form of salary advance, allowances, bonus among others are motivational tools that spurs teachers to put in extra efforts in achieving organization set goals. This, of course, influence not only effective teaching, but students learning outcomes and the overall school performance. On the other hand, lack and delay remuneration ultimately affects teachers' morale, leading to decrease in job satisfaction and increased turnover. The finding from the current study is consistent with that of Okafor (2015) which revealed that teachers who received comprehensive welfare packages reported increased motivation and teaching effectiveness, supporting the positive relationship found between welfare packages and teachers job satisfaction in the present study. This alignment is further corroborated by Udom (2017), whose research indicated that teachers in schools with consistent welfare packages displayed enhanced classroom management skills, better lesson delivery and improved student and teachers' relationships. Its, noteworthy that while the term "welfare packages" is broad, its strong correlation with job satisfaction, as enhanced by both the present study and Udom research signals its importance in the educational sector in Rivers State. Similarly, the present study is in harmony with Igbogi (2018) who found that teachers with access to better welfare packages exhibited higher commitment in terms of lesson planning, extra-curricular, involvement, and overall dedication to the teaching profession. This underscores the positive correlation between welfare packages and teachers' job satisfaction identified in the current study.

The result of in-service training and job satisfaction of teachers in research question three revealed that in-service training had a very high extent of improving the job satisfaction of teachers in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State. The third hypothesis, indicated that there is a positive relationship between in-service training and job satisfaction of teachers. The positive correlation between in-service training and teachers' job satisfaction that is revealed in the present study supports the role of teachers' development as part of the general welfare of teachers. While the empirical reviews discussed previously do not directly address in-service training, the importance of teachers' development, support, and overall welfare is a recurring theme. Ekundayo (2018) study, for instance, which showed that schools with satisfied teachers due to their welfare packages had students scoring higher on standardized tests, can be indirectly related to the premise. If teachers are receiving in-service training, it is likely part of the broader welfare or professional development package aimed at improving their skills, thus leading to job satisfaction. Chidiebere (2019) further buttresses the results of the present study, particularly regarding the role of welfare packages in job satisfaction and retention. Given the strong correlation between job satisfaction and the quality of welfare packages, it is evident that such provisions are not only pivotal for job satisfaction but also for the long term-

retention of teachers. Thus, retention and job satisfaction can lead to a more stable and productive educational environment, reinforcing the importance of addressing teachers' welfare comprehensively.

CONCLUSION

This study provided valuable insights into the relationship between welfare implementations and teacher job satisfaction, shedding light on the importance of well-designed incentive systems to attract and retain high-quality educators in the teaching profession. Our findings highlight the significant positive impact that both monetary and non-monetary incentives have on teacher job satisfaction, commitment, and long-term retention. Monetary incentives, such as competitive salaries, bonuses, and good salary, are crucial in retaining teachers by addressing financial concerns and reflecting the value society places on the profession. Non-monetary incentives, including opportunities for professional development, recognition of achievements, supportive work environments, and reduced workload, also play a vital role in enhancing teachers' job satisfaction and motivation. Therefore, fringe benefits, welfare packages and in-service training were good incentives which enhanced teachers' job satisfaction among teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study on welfare implementation and teachers' job satisfaction, the following recommendations were made:

1. Education stakeholders should provide fringe benefits both monetary and non-monetary incentives including cars for teachers. This, of course, will enhance teachers' job satisfaction, commitment and retention.
2. The state government should implement an upward review of policy on teachers' welfare packages to suit the current economic trend in the society.
3. Management of schools especially Ministry of Education should as a matter of urgency provide funds for in-service training of teachers at the secondary school level, in order to enhance their skills and knowledge for effective learning and teaching which will enhance their job satisfaction.

REFERENCES

- Abbah, M. T. (2014). Employee Motivation: The Key in Effective Organisation Management in Nigeria. *Journal of Business Management*, 16 (4), 001 – 008.
- Abu, M. N. (2016). The Role of Welfare Structure Welfare Packages on the Daily Output of Construction Workers in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*.
- Adeniji, A. A., Heisman, O. O. & Osibanjo, O. A. (2014). Compensation Packages: A Strategic Tool for Employees' Performance and Retention. *Leonardo Journal of Science*, 25 -84.
- Agboola, A. K., & Offiong, A. I. (2018). Incentives structure and teachers' job satisfaction. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(27), 10-18.
- Armstrong, P. O. (2008). *A Handbook of Human Resources Management Practice*. 10th Ed. London: Kogan Press.
- Arnold, S. (2013). The effects of teacher incentives on teacher job satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Research and Reviews*, 1(1), 9-15.
- Bernaardin, H. J. (2007). *Human Resource Management: An Experiential Approach*. Tata McGraw Hills.
- Besong, F. (2015). Welfare implementation and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 7(4), 106-112.
- Bolin, F. (2007) A Study of Teacher Job Satisfaction and Factors that Influence it. *Chinese Educational Society*, 40 (3) 47.
- Dixit, A., & Bhati, M. (2012). A study on employee retention in a construction company. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 1(4), 16-19.

- Don, O. (2013). Teacher job satisfaction strategies in the American public school system. *Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research*, 1(1), 23-28.
- Dunn, D. S. (2001). *Statistics and data analysis for the Behavioural Sciences*. New York. McGraw Hill, Higher Education.
- Echikpu, A. (2022). The relationship between welfare implementation and teacher job satisfaction in primary schools. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 10(2), 45-60.
- Eduwen, F.O. (2016). In Service Education of Teachers: Overview; Problems and the way forward. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7, 26
- Elendu, I. C. (2010). *Fundamentals of Research and Statistics for Students in Human Kinetics and other Disciplines*. The Glory of the Later House Publishing Company.
- Emenike, O. (2013). *Educational Management Theory and Practice*. Jamoe Enterprise (Nig.) Abakpa-Nike, Enugu.
- Erabasi, A. (2012). The Effect of Financial and Non-Financial Incentives on Job Satisfaction an Examination of Food Chain Premises in Turkey. *International Business Research*, 15 (10), 13 – 25.
- Ezeali, B. O. & Esiagu, L. N. (2009). Relationship between incentives and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Foundations*, 3(1), 21-29.
- Fisk, E. K. (2001). *The New Teacher's Complete Source Book: Grades K-4*. Scholastic.
- FRN (2014). *National Policy on Education*. Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council Press.
- Igbogi, I. (2008). Teachers' Welfare and Commitment as Determinants of Productivity in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 11 (6), 1041 – 1058.
- Keitanny, B. J. (2014). Perceived Relationship between Employee Welfare Programme and Employee Performance at Kenya Pipeline Company (Unpublished MBA Project). University of Nairobi.
- Kelly, S. (2014). Teacher incentives and teacher job satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Management and Policy*, 1(1), 9-16.
- Ngatia, Z. N. (2005). *The Influence of Non-Monetary Rewards on Employees Performance in Muranga*. Water and Sanitation Company, Muranga County.
- Nwankwo, O. O. (2016). *A Practical Guide to Research Writing for Students in Education and Social Science (6th Ed)*. Port Harcourt. M and I Grade Orbit and Communication Ltd.
- Nzelibe, C. G. O. (2011). *Strategic Managements, Concepts and Process*. Onitsha: Joyce Publications.
- Ogu, U. (2016). Welfare implementation and teacher job satisfaction in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Management and Policy*, 2(1), 7-14.
- Okendu, J. N. (2012). *Research and Statistics in Education*. Ibadan: Suite Foundation Prints.
- Okolo, I.A. (2013). Teachers' education: A panacea for successful transformation in Nigeria. A seminar paper presented at the 2013 National Conference of the Committee of Provost of Colleges of Education in Nigeria, Abuja
- Okumbe, J. A. (2010). *Human Resource Management*. Nairobi. AICTS Press.
- Oluwale, D. A. (2015). Teacher welfare and Quality education delivery: An assessment of Public secondary schools in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Research and Technology*, 6(1) 88-97
- Opoku – Asare, N. A., Agbenyega, J. S. & Wilmot, E. M. (2014). Teacher Job Satisfaction in Ghana: A Different Perspective. *Journal of Education and Development Psychology*, 4 (1) 198 – 212.
- Vroom, V. H. (1964). *Work and Motivation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Wali, G. I. (2016). *Educational Research: Principles and Practice*. Port Harcourt. David Store Publishers.